

Running head: *CREATIVE METACOGNITION*

PUBLISHED. The final version is available OA here:

Lebuda, I., & Benedek, M. (2023). A systematic framework of creative metacognition. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 46, 161-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2023.07.002>

A systematic framework of creative metacognition

Izabela Lebuda

University of Graz, University of Wrocław

Mathias Benedek

University of Graz

Authors' Note and Acknowledgement

Both authors contributed equally to this work and thus share the first authorship.

Corresponding authors:

Izabela Lebuda (izabela.lebuda@uni-graz.at; izabela.lebuda@uwr.edu.pl)

Mathias Benedek (mathias.benedek@uni-graz.at)

Institute of Psychology, University of Graz, Universitätsplatz 2, 8010 Graz, Austria;

Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Dawida 1, 50-527 Wrocław, Poland

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 896518

Abstract

Creative cognition does not just involve cognitive processes in direct service of the main task objective (e.g., idea generation), but also metacognitive processes that monitor and regulate cognition adaptively (e.g., evaluation of ideas and task performance, or development and selection of task strategies).

Although metacognition is vital for creative performance, relevant work is sparse, which may be partly due to persistent ambiguities in the theoretical conceptualization of creative metacognition. Therefore, this article proposes a systematic framework of creative metacognition (CMC), which builds on recent advancements in metacognition theory and extends them to meet the specifics of creative cognition.

The CMC framework consists of two dynamic components—monitoring and control—and a static component of metacognitive knowledge, each subsuming metacognitive processes applying to the level of task, performance, and responses. We describe the presumed function of these metacognitive components in the creative process, present evidence in support of each, and discuss their association with related constructs, such as creative self-beliefs. We further highlight the dynamic interplay of metacognitive processes across task performance and identify promising avenues for future research.

Keywords: creativity, metacognition, metacognitive monitoring, metacognitive control, metacognitive knowledge

1. Introduction

A central goal in creativity research is to understand cognitive mechanisms in creative cognition. Much of this work has focused on idea generation and specifically on how ideas are forged from new combinations of memory elements (Mednick, 1962). Yet, creative cognition involves more than the processes that eventually shape a creative response, but also includes evaluative and strategic processes that ensure effective application of cognitive resources, such as monitoring of task progress, reconsidering task strategies, or evaluation of candidate responses. The reflection on and regulation of one's cognitive activities—put simply: cognition on cognition—is called *metacognition* (Norman et al., 2019). While the significance of metacognition in creativity has long been acknowledged (Armbruster, 1989; Davidson et al., 1994; Davidson & Sternberg, 1998; Pesut, 1990), relevant theorizing has not advanced much since. Available models mostly focused on the interaction between idea generation and idea evaluation processes (e.g., Finke et al., 1992; Kleinmintz et al., 2019; Mumford et al., 2012). Empirical work further highlighted the relevance of cognitive strategies in creative task performance (Fleck & Weisberg, 2004; Gilhooly et al., 2007). Notably, creative problems are typically ill-defined and often have no single correct solution, which undermines the use of straightforward, analytical approaches and instead implies an evaluation of ambiguous solution criteria (Sidi et al., 2020; Silvia, 2008). Hence, metacognitive processes can be assumed to play an important role in creative cognition, and research in this field would benefit from a systematic theoretical framework of creative metacognition.

In the last decade, the topic of metacognition in creativity has re-gained interest. However, the construct still seems less popular than related forms of thinking about creativity, known as creative self-beliefs (see Karwowski & Beghetto, 2017; Karwowski, Lebuda, & Beghetto, 2019). The trend reflects itself well in the results on *google scholar* search: Prior to 2012, the data shows only 10 results for "creative metacognition," whereas the last decade (from 2012 to 2022) has displayed 358 records

already (data from 21.03.2021). Although this is a clear sign of increasing scholarly attention, it is still a drop in the ocean, compared to 8,870 records for “creative self-efficacy” (i.e., one particular creative self-belief), in the same latter period. Therefore, it seems about time to take a closer look at how people think about their creative thinking. The goal of this paper thus is to examine and formalize the structure of metacognitive processes in creativity. Based on a review of theoretical and empirical works from different subdomains and traditions of psychology, we derive a systematic framework of creative metacognition. We identify relevant metacognitive components and describe their presumed function and dynamic interplay in creative cognition.

2. Coming to Terms: Available Theorizing and Findings on Creative Metacognition

2.1. Models of metacognition

Metacognition has been recurrently conceptualized in many different disciplines of psychology. Most of them focus on learning or memory and examine metacognitive processes from educational and developmental perspectives (Norman et al., 2019). Currently, there is growing interest in the role of metacognition in more complex cognitive activities, such as reasoning, decision making, and problem solving (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017; Fleming, & Daw, 2017). These efforts are accompanied by persistent challenges regarding the conceptualization of metacognition; even in domains like educational psychology, which has a comparatively long tradition of theorizing about metacognition, questions regarding the proper structure, definition, and naming of metacognitive components are subjects of ongoing debate (e.g., Pintrich et al., 2000; Schunk, 2008; Veenman et al., 2006; Zohar & Ben David, 2009). For the sake of terminological clarity, we present the main theoretical works that have inspired our understanding of creative metacognition.

One particularly well-known framework in the field of metacognition is Stanovich’s *Triple Model of Mind* (Stanovich, 2012). It was designed to extend dual-processes theories, which assume the interplay of two types of processes—fast, automatic, spontaneous (Type 1), and slow, controlled,

analytical (Type 2) processes—by including higher intellectual, reflective functions associated with rationality (rational mind). Rationality is a thinking disposition that relies on beliefs, goals, and general knowledge, and is responsible for initializing or overriding standard cognitive processes (Evans & Stanovich, 2013). Highly rational people are characterized by well-calibrated beliefs and actions facilitating the achievement of their goals. Consequently, individual differences in performance arise from differences in cognitive abilities as well as from differences in how effectively those cognitive abilities are applied (i.e., metacognitive skills), which partly explains why highly able people are not always successful in their endeavors (e.g., DeCaro et al., 2011). Considering the role of metacognition in this way could also enhance our understanding of individual differences in such complex cognitive functions as creativity.

A presumed structure of metacognition has been described in some detail in the classical and still influential proposition by the developmental and cognitive psychologist Flavell (1979). He assumed that solving any cognitive task requires proper strategies—actions towards achieving a goal—which involves two main metacognitive components: A static component called *metacognitive knowledge* and a dynamic component called *metacognitive experience*. Metacognitive knowledge refers to explicit information (correct and incorrect) related to tasks and strategies stored in long-term memory, which is relatively stable (Frazier et al., 2021; Kuhn, 2021). It is thought to contain three types of information regarding tasks and strategies: declarative information that answers the question “what?” (e.g., what type of strategy is appropriated in a particular task?), procedural information that answers the question “how?” (e.g., how to implement different strategies?), and conditional information that answers the questions “when and why?” (e.g., when to use a strategy?) (Pintrich et al., 2000). Unlike metacognitive knowledge, *metacognitive experience* is conceived as a dynamic metacognitive component that reflects ongoing cognitive activities which involve working memory. Metacognitive experience has a reciprocal relationship with metacognitive knowledge: “Some metacognitive experience is best described as items

of metacognitive knowledge that have entered consciousness” (Flavell, 1979, p. 908), while experiences will also contribute to updating and extending metacognitive knowledge.

Some theories of metacognition focus on metacognitive experience, without including metacognitive knowledge. One of them is the proposition of *meta-reasoning*, which describes metacognition during such complex tasks as decision making and problem solving (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017). This framework relies on seminal work on the role of metacognition in memory (Nelson & Narens, 1994), where the cognitive process is split into two interrelated levels: object-level and meta-level. The object-level refers to the overarching objective of a cognitive performance (e.g., learning, or problem-solving), while the meta-level is conceived as dynamic, mental simulation of the object-level that contains two distinct facets: monitoring and control (e.g., judgment of knowing, or allocation of the study time) (Nelson, 1990; Nelson & Narens, 1994). Metacognitive monitoring represents the subjective assessment of how a task was, is, and/or will be performed (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017; Efklides, 2006). Regarding task demands, one recently examined aspect is the *judgment of solvability*, which refers to the evaluation of how likely a task can be solved successfully in given time. It is usually assessed at the beginning of the process (*initial judgment of solvability*), but also at the end of it (*final judgment of solvability*)—even if someone cannot respond to the task, a person can assess whether it is doable for others on the next attempt or in a different context (Ackerman & Beller, 2017; Ackerman & Thompson, 2017). Similarly, people can judge their task performance in terms of perceived *confidence*, which may fluctuate over the course of the task, and thus is often assessed at different stages (i.e., *initial*, *intermediate*, and *final confidence*; Ackerman, 2014; Metcalfe & Wiebe, 1987; Shekhar & Rahnev, 2021a). Evaluations of specific solutions that come to mind can be assessed in terms of *feelings of rightness* or *feelings of error* (see Ackerman & Thompson, 2017), and the more general, experience-based judgment of one’s own cognitive actions has been referred to as *metacognitive feelings* (Efklides, 2006; Koriat & Levy-Sadot, 1999). All these monitoring aspects reflect

the perceived (un)certainty of the successful unfolding of task performance. The mentioned indicators of metacognitive monitoring are not exhaustive, but many other specialized forms of monitoring have been proposed in the context of memory, learning, and knowledge acquisition (e.g., feeling of knowing, judgment of learning; Koriat, 1993, 1997), which cannot be covered comprehensively here for the sake of space and focus.

As metacognitive monitoring evaluates the expected success in task performance, it helps to decide on whether to persist in or desist from cognitive efforts and thus serves as a basis for *metacognitive control*. This subcomponent is responsible for adjusting such cognitive processes as starting, finishing, or changing effort allocation during cognitive tasks (Ackerman, 2019; Ackerman & Thompson, 2017). The main activities that constitute metacognitive control are resource administration (i.e., engaging in or giving up on a task, or seeking help), developing, selecting, or adapting strategies, and deciding on either reporting or reconsidering a chosen solution (Lieder & Griffiths, 2017).

The activity of the two metacognitive experience components—monitoring and control—can thus be considered interdependent: The outcomes of monitoring, which are not always reliable, lead to recalibration of cognitive effort, and the effects of this exertion are monitored again to make subsequent decisions (Ackerman, 2019; Koriat et al., 2006). Both metacognitive monitoring and control are also dependent on the complexity of the object-level process (e.g., reasoning, decision making, problem-solving). As a result, metacognitive experience components dynamically adjust to the requirements of the cognitive challenge at hand (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017). Finally, metacognitive knowledge is assumed to support both monitoring and control processes by offering access to information that facilitates more accurate evaluations and more informed decisions (Horn et al., 1993; Nietfeld & Schraw, 2002). In sum, metacognition during task performance unfolds from the interplay of

a more static part of metacognitive knowledge and a more dynamic part of metacognitive experience involving metacognitive monitoring and control.

2.2. Available theorizing on creative metacognition

The relevance of metacognitive processes in creativity has long been postulated (Armbruster, 1989; Davidson et al., 1994; Davidson & Sternberg, 1998; Pesut, 1990). Its significance becomes particularly evident in popular *Generation-Evaluation* models, which posit that creative ideas result from an interplay of generative and evaluative processes (Campbell, 1960; Finke et al., 1992; Kleinmintz et al., 2019; Mumford et al., 2012), with evaluation processes referring to an important aspect of metacognitive monitoring. For example, the *Blind-Variation-Selective-Retention (BVSR)* hypothesis proposes that creative ideas result from iterative shifts between unguided variations of solution attempts and the selection of improved solutions (Campbell, 1960; Simonton, 2011). Similarly, the *Geneplore* model assumes that creative cognition involves cyclic phases of divergent generation (where preinventive structures are created) and convergent exploration (through which these structures get explored and interpreted; Finke, 1996). Along these lines, research that explicitly targeted creative metacognition mostly focused on a person's ability to accurately evaluate the creativity of their own ideas (e.g., Karwowski et al., 2020; Puente-Diaz et al., 2022). Hence, response monitoring has been recognized as an essential process in creative ideation, but relevant theorizing has not framed it in the context of metacognition, while empirical works on creative metacognition tend to equate creative metacognition with creativity evaluation.

Further theoretical models highlight differences in task strategies, thereby pointing to the significance of metacognitive control in creative cognition. For example, the *dual pathway to creativity* model assumes that creativity is supported by either cognitive flexibility (i.e., exploring many different content categories) or cognitive persistence (i.e., exploring few content categories in great depth) —two

modes of thinking that can be affected by dispositional and situational factors (De Dreu et al., 2008; Nijstad et al., 2010). According to the *metacontrol state* model, which views cognitive control as emerging from the interaction of two counteracting forces (Hommel, 2015), metacontrol biases towards flexibility should be especially beneficial for divergent thinking and creative problem solving with insight, whereas metacontrol biases towards persistence should benefit convergent thinking (Zhang et al., 2020). Like the dual pathway model, optimal foraging theory (Hills et al., 2012) views creative ideation as search in a meaning landscape that involves both exploration and exploitation behavior (Hart et al., 2018; viz., switching and clustering; Ovando-Tellez et al., 2022). Together, these models point to the relevance of metacognitive control processes in creativity.

The first and only explicit definition of creative metacognition to date was formulated by Kaufman and Beghetto (2013), who described it as “a combination of creative self-knowledge (knowing one’s own creative strengths and limitations, both within a domain and as a general trait) and contextual knowledge (knowing when, where, how, and why to be creative)” (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2013, p. 160). They argued that creativity is not always expected or needed, and could be even punished, so understanding when to display one’s own ability could maximize benefits and minimize costs of creative behaviors. This view on creative metacognition emphasizes implications for educational and other practical contexts (e.g., Hofer et al., 2022), linking individual abilities with socio-cultural demands and highlighting the need for developing skill recognition and the ability to manage those demands adaptively according to given circumstances. This view on creative metacognition thus takes a broad perspective, which addresses aspects of creative self-regulation (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017; Zielińska et al., 2022), but without delineating specific (meta)cognitive processes in creative performance comprehensively. Metacognition and self-regulation are similar in that they are viewed as effortful psychological processes that guide goal-directed activities; however, these constructs are not interchangeable (for discussion, see Dinsmore et al., 2008; Frazier et al., 2021; Kaplan, 2008; and see

Koriat et al., 2006, for a different view). Metacognition, as the name suggests, focuses on task-relevant cognitive processes. In contrast, self-regulation is a more global and inclusive concept that emphasizes emotional, motivational, and behavioral regulation and coordinates the interaction between person and environment (Bandura, 1986; Frazier et al., 2021; Urban & Urban, 2022). Hence, while creative metacognition focuses on the thinking process, creative self-regulation goes beyond cognitive aspects by considering, for instance, long-term efforts of translating an idea into observable results (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017; Rubenstein et al., 2018; Zielińska et al., 2022). Metacognition is thus one of the sources that inform self-regulation (Efklides, 2011; Frazier et al., 2021; Zimmerman, 2013). These two concepts are also embedded in different theoretical traditions: Metacognition is linked more to cognitive science and as such, at least partly assessed by performance-based tests, whereas self-regulation is more rooted in social and personality science, perceived as trait-like characteristic, and is therefore assessed most often with self-report scales (Dinsmore et al., 2008; Malanchini et al., 2019).

In sum, available theoretical frameworks of creative cognition have clearly implicated the relevance of metacognitive processes by highlighting the crucial role of idea evaluation processes and of differences task strategies in creative performance. The first explicit model of creative metacognition focused on questions regarding when to apply one's own creativity, which partly refers to the important domain of creative self-regulation, as well as on convictions about one's own creativity, which refers to the field of creative self-beliefs (Karwowski & Kaufman, 2017; Karwowski, Lebeda, & Beghetto, 2019). So far, however, we still lack a comprehensive systematic framework of creative metacognition that is consistent with established metacognition theories and describes the structure and function of metacognitive processes in creative cognition.

3. A systematic framework of creative metacognition (CMC)

3.1. General aims

This section presents a systematic framework of creative metacognition that builds on the rich theoretical advancements in relevant fields of psychology and extends them to meet the specifics of creative cognition. We start by outlining central components of creative metacognition, then we examine their function in cognition as well as available evidence in support of their relevance, and finally we explore their dynamic interplay over the course of creative task performance.

Creative thinking, and especially creative ideation as assessed by divergent thinking tasks, differs from most other forms of problem-solving (e.g., reasoning) in at least two important ways: First, divergent thinking tasks ask to find creative (or original) ideas rather than correct solutions. Second, divergent thinking tasks ask people to come up with several responses rather than a single response. These two central affordances of creative ideation require people to, firstly, understand what is considered creative and thus to evaluate and select their own responses accordingly. Secondly, they have to navigate an open-ended solution space of unclear size and thus decide whether and how the task should be continued to find even more creative responses. Hence, creative cognition arguably implies unique metacognitive challenges of how to direct cognitive resources effectively during creative task performance. For this reason, the framework focuses on creativity especially in terms of creative ideation (viz. divergent thinking creativity), and less on creative problem solving (viz. convergent thinking creativity)—tasks with correct solutions that are typically solved via mental reframing and sometimes involve subjective experiences of insight (Gilhooly & Murphy, 2005)— which has already been studied in the context of metacognition of general problem solving and reasoning (e.g., Ackerman & Beller, 2017; Danek et al., 2016; Danek & Wiley, 2020; Metcalfe, 1986; Metcalfe & Wiebe, 1987). In the following, we will use the term “creative metacognition” as a short form for metacognition in creativity. Of course, this does not mean to imply that the metacognitive process is creative in itself but

rather pays tribute to the tradition of nomenclature in the psychology of creativity: Self-beliefs regarding creativity are typically called “creative self-beliefs” (Beghetto & Karwowski, 2017; Karwowski, Lebeda, & Beghetto, 2019) and contain subcomponents named “creative personal identity”, “creative self-concept”, “creative self-efficacy”, “creative mindsets”. Moreover, the term “creative metacognition” has been established by Kaufman and Beghetto (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2013) and became widely accepted by other researchers (e.g., Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2020; Urban & Urban, 2021).

3.2. Structure of creative metacognition

The proposed framework of creative metacognition (CMC) consists of separate dynamic and static metacognitive components that complement and interact with cognitive processes focused on the main task objective (see Figure 1, for an overview). To distinguish these two types of cognitive processes we will refer to them as core cognitive process (CCP; also known as object-level cognition; Nelson & Narens, 1994) versus metacognitive processes (MCP) as ones that directly versus indirectly advance creative task performance, respectively. For instance, if the main task objective is, to generate creative uses for an object like a car tire (i.e., alternate uses task; Torrance, 1974), CCPs are thought to involve memory search for *problem-relevant knowledge* and recombination of this information to generate novel object uses (Benedek & Fink, 2019; Mumford et al., 2012). Problem-relevant knowledge usually includes knowledge related to the specific problem at hand (e.g., semantic and episodic knowledge about car tires, such as that they are round and flexible, and sometimes adapted as a swing), as well as new and potentially unrelated information that is connected or reconstructed with problem-related information to produce a new and effective solution (Beatty & Schacter, 2018; Benedek, Könen, & Neubauer, 2012; Kenett & Faust, 2019; Weisberg, 2020). In contrast, MCPs direct the application of CCPs, such as selecting a specific task strategy that implies *how* information is searched and combined as well as evaluation of ideas and general task progress. Consistent with other models of metacognition (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017; Efklides, 2006; Nelson & Narens, 1994), we assume that MCPs can be

divided into processes of *metacognitive monitoring* and *metacognitive control*. Monitoring and control processes are viewed as interdependent, with monitoring informing control processes and control processes informing the targets of monitoring. Finally, these dynamic metacognitive processes rely on metacognitive knowledge such as knowing specific creative tasks and strategies, which eventually gets updated by new experiences acquired during creative task performance (see Figure 1).

Figure 1.

A dynamic framework of creative metacognition (CMC). The CMC framework describes metacognitive processes (MCPs; yellow boxes) that complement core cognitive processes (CCPs; gray boxes). Creative metacognition consists of two dynamic components of metacognitive control and metacognitive monitoring associated with working memory, and a static component of metacognitive knowledge associated with long-term memory. Specific metacognitive processes at the levels of task, performance,

and responses are outlined for each component (see subtext in boxes). The presumed relations between all components across creative task performance are indicated by arrows.

3.2.1. Metacognitive monitoring in creative performance

Metacognitive (MC) monitoring represents a set of evaluative processes at different levels of granularity (i.e., levels of task, performance, and responses; see Figure 1). First, it involves building a representation of the creative task and evaluating general task characteristics, for instance, in terms of its familiarity, difficulty, etc. (*MC monitoring at task level*: evaluation of task characteristics). Second, *MC monitoring at performance level* involves an evaluation of task performance, which can take place prior to and after task engagement (i.e., confidence to perform well/have performed well in the task; Beghetto & Karwowski, 2017; Karwowski, Han, & Beghetto, 2019). Additionally, a dynamic monitoring of task performance and progress over the course of the task is assumed, which typically results in feelings regarding ease and fluency of task performance (cf. metacognitive feelings; Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2022). In creative ideation, monitoring of ongoing task performance would detect when a person, for instance, runs out of ideas. Importantly, assessments of task performance reflect performance goals as defined in task instructions, which can vary substantially in divergent thinking tasks. Task instructions can either focus on response quality (be creative!), response quantity (find many/different ideas!), or both (i.e., hybrid/mixed instruction: e.g., find as many and as creative ideas as possible!; Reiter-Palmon et al., 2019). Hybrid instructions pose a particular challenge as they imply a dual task setting, where people need to balance their cognitive resources to meet both sub-goals (i.e., finding many *and* creative ideas). Third, generation of new candidate ideas instantiates evaluations of those responses (*MC monitoring at response level*: evaluation of candidate responses), which assesses whether a specific response meets the requirements of the task (e.g., find novel object uses; don't repeat responses; be creative). The evaluation of the creativity of responses is especially challenging as there is no objective criterion of creativity and the creative worth of ideas varies across time and cultural

context (Glaveanu et al., 2020; Karwowski, 2016). Instead, creativity evaluation requires assessing such various potentially ambiguous criteria as whether it is novel, original, effective, interesting, humorous etc., which are rarely explicitly mentioned in task instructions (Silvia, 2008). Consequently, people rely on their subjective conceptions of what is considered creative, which can vary substantially (e.g., would bizarre or dark responses be considered creative?). In creative problem-solving tasks, which have a single correct response (e.g., insight tasks; Gilhooly & Murphy, 2005), evaluation of candidate responses is more straightforward as the response should evidently be correct or incorrect. Especially for tasks requiring reframing of task sets, solutions often appear tentative and thus involve a final evaluation (viz., verification) of the solution (Ohlsson, 1992). Besides immediate response evaluations during the task, an additional idea evaluation process can take place at the end of task performance, when one is required to identify a certain number of top ideas as final response (Benedek et al., 2013; Silvia et al., 2008). These three types of monitoring processes thus refer to different levels of assessment (e.g., “Is this task requiring creativity?” vs. “Am I performing well in this creativity task?” vs. “Is this response creative?”). Yet, these levels inform each other, as finding an idea that is considered highly creative (evaluation of candidate response), would favorably update the assessment of task performance (e.g., I’m performing better than expected), and eventually also update the general task evaluation (e.g., the task is less difficult than I thought; Karwowski, Han, & Beghetto, 2019; Puente-Diaz, Cavazos-Arroyo, & Vargas-Barrera, 2021).

While we are not aware of much research that explored effects of *MC monitoring at task level* (evaluation of task characteristics), there is substantial work related to *MC monitoring at performance level* (evaluation of task performance). Evaluation outcomes can be measured in different ways including absolute accuracy, relative accuracy, and bias of judgements (Schraw, 2009). Absolute accuracy refers to the discrepancy between judgements and performance (e.g., absolute difference to criterion), whereas relative accuracy refers to covariation of judgements and performance (e.g.,

correlation with criterion). In contrast, bias refers to the over- versus underestimation of judgements (e.g., signed difference to criterion). Relevant work found that people tend to overestimate their creative performance in divergent thinking and creative problem solving (Pesout & Nietfeld, 2021; cf. in insight problem solving – Metcalfe & Wiebe, 1987; but see, Kaufman et al., 2016); however, overconfidence appears to be less pronounced compared to other non-creative domains (Dunlosky & Rawson, 2012; Kruger & Dunning, 1999; Metcalfe, 1998). Assessments of creative performance are further moderated by individual differences: Creative people are more accurate in their overall assessments of creative performance (Kaufman et al., 2013; Pesout & Nietfeld, 2021). However, people with higher tendency to perceive a meaningless statement as profound (also called *bullshit receptivity*; George & Mielicki, 2022) are less accurate in predicting their creativity both in divergent and convergent thinking tasks, whereas assessments of performances in verbal analogy or recall tasks were unaffected (George & Mielicki, 2022).

Interestingly, initial evaluations of creative task performance (pre-task confidence) are also sensitive to subtle external cues. For example, using a visual stimulus rather than a text stimulus of an everyday object in the AUT led to higher confidence (feeling that a creative idea will emerge easily), even though it actually biased performance toward more obvious solutions (George et al., 2021; cf. Chrysikou et al., 2016). A similar effect was found in the creative problem-solving context (RAT): Exposition to cue-associations increased confidence in the ability to solve the task, but induced fixation and resulted in poorer problem solving (Storm & Hickman, 2015). These findings suggest that having more specific information about the problem appears helpful and thereby increases confidence (metacognitive monitoring of expected task performance), while at the same time this additional information may actually increase the chance of cognitive fixation and thereby impair performance. This result pattern suggests an interesting misalignment of metacognitive monitoring and performance (higher confidence associated with poorer performance).

Evaluations of task performance during and after a task were found to reflect such heuristic clues as perceived ease of processing, accessibility, or familiarity of information (Ackerman, 2019). The relevance of these experience-based clues (Koriat & Levy-Sadot, 1999, 2001; cf., metacognitive experiences; Efklides, 2006) was also observed in creativity research: Slight reductions of processing fluency induced by moderate ambient noise resulted in more abstract processing and thereby improved creative ideation, whereas performance suffered during exposition to strong noise (Mehta et al., 2012). Similarly, ambient music with different semantic content was found to impair creative problem solving (Threadgold et al., 2019). Therefore, while external distraction typically impairs creative performance likely by reducing relevant cognitive resources, reduced processing fluency may still have beneficial effects under specific conditions. Another study showed that feelings of low fluency caused by a decreasing number of generated ideas over time results in underestimating subsequent performance in terms of not expecting that originality of ideas would further increase with time (Lucas & Nordgren, 2015; see also Lucas & Nordgren, 2020). In contrast, higher self-reported ease and flow in the process of idea generation (i.e., conceived as more positive *metacognitive feelings*) was associated with an overestimation of own ideas and less accurate idea selections, thereby showing effects from monitoring of performance level to response level (Puente-Diaz, Cavazos-Arroyo, & Vargas-Barrera, 2021, but see Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2020). Together, these findings reveal interesting inaccuracies and biases that appear largely specific to creative cognition.

Regarding *MC monitoring at response level* (evaluation of candidate responses), there has also been much interest in examining idea evaluation accuracy (i.e., how discerning are people in identifying their creative ideas?). Crucially, since there is no objective criterion of an idea's creativity, it appears recommended to assess its relative accuracy (aka. resolution or discernment) in terms of the extent of agreement between judgements and criteria as well as the evaluation bias (aka. calibration) for given time and context (e.g., group of external judges or pool of responses; Silvia, 2008; cf. Ceh et al., 2022).

The (relative) evaluation accuracy for assessing response creativity (i.e., creativity evaluation skill) has been studied extensively with respect to judging one's own and others' ideas (for a review, see Guo et al., 2022). Overall, creative people appear doubly skilled: Those who are more creative are also more discerning in idea evaluation (Grohman et al., 2006; Runco & Smith, 1992; Silvia, 2008). Effects are stronger for evaluation of own ideas, but they also hold for evaluation of others' ideas, where a confound with performance is avoided (i.e., more creative people generate and thus get to judge more responses and more creative responses; Benedek et al., 2016; Ceh et al., 2022). Higher intelligence also predicted more accurate originality judgements of one's own ideas suggesting that general cognitive ability plays a role in metacognitive monitoring (Karwowski et al., 2020). Neuroscientific work showed that more accurate and effective monitoring at the response level is associated with lower parietal alpha activity potentially reflecting increased external attention associated with the thorough evaluation of own ideas (Rominger et al., 2022). Importantly, the reflection about one's own ideas was found to translate into better performance in not only creative thinking tasks, but also in applied design tasks (Hao et al., 2016; Wetzstein & Hacker, 2004). Moreover, professionals more often than lay people engage in monitoring activities (Fayena-Tawil et al., 2011) and assessment accuracy develops with increasing experience (Kleinmintz et al., 2014; Kozbelt, 2007). Together, these findings suggest that metacognitive monitoring at response level supports creative performance.

People appear reasonably discerning in judging which ideas are more creative than others; they even notice that creativity of their own ideas increases with task duration (Sidi et al., 2020), which is known as the serial-order effect (Beaty & Silvia, 2012). These judgements rely much more on an idea's originality than on its effectiveness (Diedrich et al., 2015), despite individual differences in these weights (Donzallaz et al., 2021). In total, people still tend to underestimate the creativity of ideas (Müller et al., 2012): They underrate the uniqueness of their ideas (Sidi et al., 2020) and find it hard to reliably assess the effectiveness of ideas (Benedek et al., 2016). Together, these miscalibrations undermine the

accuracy of creativity evaluations and potentially render them more susceptible to external influences. Indeed, response monitoring is sensitive to feedback, as false positive and negative feedback resulted in higher and lower evaluations of response originality, respectively, whereas feedback did not affect creative performance (Sidi et al., 2020). In another experiment, the authors manipulated the performance by presenting a high versus low anchor in task instructions (2 versus 6 responses); people instructed with a higher anchor increased response fluency but actually showed impaired creativity evaluations (Sidi et al., 2020). This study nicely demonstrates the possibility of separately impacting idea generation and monitoring. This again highlights the distinction between core cognitive and metacognitive processes, thereby enabling a double dissociation, as previously demonstrated in other domains (Metcalfe & Finn, 2008).

3.2.2. Metacognitive control in creative performance

Metacognitive control represents a second set of metacognitive processes that broadly guide the application of core cognitive processes. It usually gets invoked when metacognitive monitoring detects the necessity to make specific decisions or to reconsider the current task approach. Again, we can delineate metacognitive control processes at three levels of granularity (see Figure 1). First, control is involved in decisions regarding task engagement, that is, whether to start and when to eventually end task engagement (*MC control at task level*: control of task engagement). The latter is especially relevant in creative ideation, where tasks often have extended durations and sometimes even take place in an untimed fashion to avoid effects of time-pressure and to support intrinsic motivation (i.e., game-like assessments; Wallach & Kogan, 1965). Also, unlike in most cognitive problem solving, where finding the correct solution would immediately terminate task engagement, in creative ideation there is no single correct solution, and so one never really knows whether it is possible to find even more creative responses in a reasonable time. Decisions as to whether it is worth staying engaged on the task are informed by the monitoring of task performance. Second, metacognitive control also plays an important

role in guiding task performance by selecting and eventually changing task strategies during the task (*MC control at performance level: control of task strategies*). As creative thinking tasks are ill-defined, they usually cannot be solved by means of a straightforward analytical strategy, but task-specific strategies often have to be developed on the spot (Gilhooly et al., 2007). Devising new task strategies requires considerable time investment, as core processes related to idea generation are largely on hold during strategy development. Further, metacognitive control is involved in decisions about when to change the strategy (i.e., regulation). Again, this decision is likely informed by metacognitive monitoring of task performance under the chosen strategy (e.g., how easily new ideas can be generated). On a more general level, maintaining versus changing a strategy relates to exploitation versus exploration behavior (Hart et al., 2018; aka. clustering and switching; Hass, 2017; persistence versus flexibility; Nijstad et al., 2010), which can be seen as meta-strategies to optimally forage open-ended search spaces (Hills et al., 2012). Third, metacognitive control is also involved in controlling response production, that is deciding whether or not a candidate response should be reported, further elaborated, or dismissed (*MC control at response level: control of response production*). This decision is thought to rely on prior evaluation of the candidate response.

There is only little research on relevant to *MC control at task level (control of task engagement)*. Available findings suggest that, whereas the number and quality of ideas naturally increases with task duration (Said-Metwaly et al., 2020), the time people stay on an untimed creative task is not directly related to their independently assessed creativity (Plucker et al., 2006).

Regarding *MC control of task performance (control of task strategies)*, think-aloud studies have revealed specific strategies used in divergent thinking (Gilhooly et al., 2007; Matheson & Kenett, 2021), creative problem solving (Fleck & Weisberg, 2004; Smith et al., 2013), visual production (Hart et al., 2018; Jankowska et al., 2018), and design (Pringle, & Sowden, 2017; Vieira et al., 2022). For example, a

detailed analysis of verbal protocols during performance of the alternate uses task showed that participants engage in task-unspecific strategies, such as trying to recall solutions from memory or self-cuing, as well as in task-specific strategies, such as focusing on specific object properties or object parts (Gilhooly et al., 2007). Importantly, while simple, unspecific strategies like memory recall resulted in a higher number of ideas, more complex, task-specific strategies, such as disassembly use, resulted in more original ideas. Studies further observed evidence for adaptive shifts of strategies over time: People often start with simple memory-based strategies before moving to more complex strategies that enable more novel and thus creative ideas (Benedek et al., 2014; Gilhooly et al., 2007). These dynamic trends towards more effective strategy usage can be considered as a driving mechanism of creativity increases over time, known as the *serial-order effect* (Beatty & Silvia, 2012). Available evidence further suggests that effective strategies are cognitively demanding and thus supported by higher executive ability and intelligence (Forthmann et al., 2016; Gilhooly et al., 2007; Nusbaum & Silvia, 2011; cf. Benedek & Jauk, 2019). People also differ in their meta-strategies, that is, their tendency to focus either on exploitation or exploration behavior, with the former being associated with a higher quantity of ideas and the latter with higher originality of ideas (Hart et al., 2017, 2022). In sum, investing MC control to find and realize more complex task strategies facilitates the generation of more creative ideas.

Further work has shed light on the control of task performance by means of experimental manipulations. People can effectively regulate their ideation performance consistently with instructions to either be creative or fluent (for a review, see Acar et al., 2020). Specifically, when instructed to be creative, people generate more creative responses at the cost of lower idea fluency (Forthmann et al., 2016; Harrington, 1975). Performance under the 'be creative' instruction is more strongly related to intelligence (Nusbaum et al., 2014), suggesting that engagement in more demanding strategies involves higher cognitive control. Yet, other lines of research investigated effects of providing example responses in task instructions on subsequent task performance. This work finds that providing examples can, on

the one hand, constrain creative performance by providing salient concepts that may cause cognitive fixation (Smith et al., 1993; Smith & Blankenship, 1991), but on the other hand, it may also support creative performance by implying relevant ideation strategies and new starting points (Agogue et al., 2014; George et al., 2019; Marsh et al., 1996). Even providing uncreative examples together with an instruction to avoid them typically increases creativity (George et al., 2019; Shin et al., 2020), unless visual examples are used, which may be too salient to overcome (George & Wiley, 2020; cf. Beaty et al., 2017). These findings show that examples may be helpful to apply more informed, effective strategies, especially when examples are put in context.

Some available research concerns *MC control at response level* (control of response production). Findings of ‘be creative’ versus ‘be fluent’ effects can also be interpreted in that people effectively screen out less creative ideas under ‘be creative’ instructions that would be reported under ‘be fluent’ instructions (Acar et al., 2020), but people may still differ in their individual thresholds (i.e., whether a moderately creative response should be reported under the ‘be creative’ instruction). This is relevant as it is debated whether response fluency drives creativity beyond scoring artifacts (cf. equal-odds-ratio; e.g., Forthmann et al., 2020), such as by freeing cognitive resources when not suppressing ideas or by increased feelings of fluent performance. People may also differ in how much effort they spend on response elaboration, that is investing resources in selling a potentially modest idea higher (Sternberg & Lubart, 1992). These decisions can pay off, because more elaborate responses are typically judged as more creative by others (Forthmann et al., 2019). In sum, applying MC control seems to have mostly positive effects on creative task performance across the three levels of investigation.

3.2.3. Metacognitive knowledge in creative performance

Metacognitive knowledge is a more static component of creative metacognition, which can again be conceived at the levels of task, performance, and responses (see Figure 1). *MC knowledge at*

task level (knowledge of creative tasks) refers to familiarity with certain tasks or problems requiring creative thinking (e.g., knowing the AUT, or the candle problem; Duncker, 1945). *MC knowledge at performance level* (knowledge of creative task strategies) involves task-specific strategies for given creative thinking tasks (e.g., disassembly strategy in the AUT), but also such task-general strategies as for instance knowing the brainstorming technique. Besides declarative knowledge on what strategies are available, it further includes procedural knowledge, that is, knowing how and when to apply certain strategies. Finally, *MC knowledge at response level* (knowledge of what is creative) refers to knowing when an idea or product can be considered creative. In the widest sense, metacognitive knowledge thus reflects the degree of creative expertise, with more professional expertise being typically more specialized to a given creative domain (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009). Consideration of MC knowledge seems particularly relevant in creative cognition for several reasons. On the one hand, creativity is a ubiquitous phenomenon that permeates all areas of life, which implies that there is plenty of opportunity to acquire knowledge about creativity; on the other hand, however, much of what people believe to know about creativity does not come from first-hand experience or scientific sources, but rather from anecdotal reports about creative genius that contribute to myths and thus to inaccurate knowledge about creativity (Benedek et al., 2021). Moreover, the role of knowledge and expertise in creativity has been subject to long-standing debates, as knowledge is viewed as both a foundation and a potentially limiting factor of creativity: While knowledge typically supports creativity, it also makes it difficult to overcome the known (Smith & Blankenship, 1991), which may not only apply to problem-relevant knowledge, but also to metacognitive knowledge on how to approach a creative task.

Research relevant to the *MC knowledge at task level* (knowledge of creative tasks) has not directly studied effects of task familiarity, but focused more specifically on familiarity with solutions to those tasks. To this end, several studies had participants first perform divergent thinking tasks and afterwards indicate whether their responses were drawn from memory (either from personal

experience or vicarious learning; Runco & Acar, 2010) or generated on the spot during the task. As noted before, people who recalled more responses from memory also had a higher total number of responses (i.e., idea fluency; Gilhooly et al., 2007; Runco & Acar, 2010), but recalled ideas were usually less creative and the number of recalled responses decreased with time on task (Benedek et al., 2014, 2018; Gilhooly et al., 2007). Interestingly, having more “old” ideas was also related to having more “new” ideas (Runco & Acar, 2010; Silvia et al., 2017), suggesting that producing many known solutions may not just be a sign of poor metacognitive control (i.e., choosing an ineffective strategy), but instead may also indicate high metacognitive knowledge relevant to the task, which may eventually inspire new, creative solutions.

Research on *MC knowledge at the performance level* (knowledge about task strategies) has employed subject-matter knowledge tests, but without considering how well this knowledge is calibrated (Antonietti et al., 2000; Pintrich et al., 2000). For example, higher knowledge about task strategies was found to compensate for a lower level of problem-solving ability (Swanson, 1990). MC knowledge is assumed to inform MC control processes by offering relevant strategies to select from, which also saves time that would otherwise be needed to devise task strategies. Yet, simply telling someone to use a strategy is not always sufficient, as people may still lack relevant implicit knowledge or cognitive capacity to implement it effectively (Nusbaum & Silvia, 2011). But teaching creative strategies in a comprehensive training was shown to increase creative performance (Hargrove & Nietfeld, 2015).

People adhere to many incorrect beliefs regarding cognitive processes underlying creativity (Benedek et al., 2021). One of the most resonating aspects of lay conception is underestimating the value of cognitive control, thus believing falsely that creativity is merely facilitated by a defocused, relaxed state accompanied by a positive mood (Baas et al., 2015). These improper convictions can misinform people’s decisions, such as conditions and circumstances they choose to be creative (Baas et

al., 2015). For example, if people erroneously believe that creativity of ideas declines over time, they are less persistent in the creative generation process, come up with fewer ideas, and with less creative ideas (Lucas & Nordgren, 2020). This confusion of declining idea productivity with a decline in idea originality (called the *creative cliff illusion*) nicely illustrates how inadequate MC knowledge can misinform MC monitoring (people assume that creativity declines across the task, although it actually increases), which eventually affects MC control (premature termination of the process as presented above). The effect remains when an assessment is done after idea generation, but it can be reduced by telling people about the effect and presented data regarding dissociation between productivity and performance judgment (Lucas & Nordgren, 2020), suggesting that improved MC knowledge counteracts the effect.

Research relevant to *MC knowledge at response level* (knowledge of what is creative) showed that having valid creativity conceptions (i.e., knowing relevant indicators of creativity) helps laypeople to evaluate creative products more effectively (Rietzschel et al., 2010). Moreover, personal experience with a divergent thinking task resulted in more accurate evaluations of idea creativity (van Broekhoven et al., 2022). These findings indicate that MC knowledge at the response level informs MC monitoring in terms of supporting discernment in creative idea evaluation. Further studies examined interventions aiming to increase metacognitive knowledge across different levels. For example, a comprehensive training session that focused on increasing knowledge about the concept, strategies, task, and assessment of creativity increased divergent thinking performance in visual arts students in terms of higher fluency and flexibility whereas originality of ideas as not affected (van de Kamp et al., 2015). We can conclude that well-calibrated metacognitive knowledge is crucial for supporting effective monitoring and control of the creative process.

It has been proposed that creative metacognition knowledge also contains such self-beliefs as creative mindsets and creative self-efficacy (Puente-Diaz, Cavazos-Arroyo, & Puerta-Sierra, 2021).

Creative mindsets refer to people's beliefs whether creativity is acquired and, as such, could be developed (growth, malleable mindset), or it is an inborn entity characteristic (fixed mindset) (Karwowski, 2014). Creative mindsets, just as metacognitive knowledge, can be retrieved from long-term memory and impact how individuals engage in the creative process (e.g., O'Connor et al., 2013; Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2017): A growth mindset is positively linked to efficiency in creative problem solving, but only among people who do not hold strong fixed mindsets at the same time (Karwowski, 2014). People characterized by high growth minds, low fixed mindsets, and high personal identity are more accurate in idea selection (Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2021). Notably, creative mindsets refer to broad beliefs about creativity (Karwowski, Lebuda, & Beghetto, 2019), but do not focus on cognition or on specific tasks and thus provide little guidance to CCPs beyond general task motivation. Therefore, creative mindsets are conceived as related but still distinct from creative MC knowledge (Anderson & Haney, 2021). *Creative self-efficacy*, referring to the expectation to perform at a particular level in a given creative activity, in turn, is strongly task- and situation-related, and thus easily affected by one's own performance (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2017). Creative self-efficacy appears especially related to MC monitoring in terms of promoting positive evaluation of anticipated performance; the crucial difference is that the former reflects a judgment of capability (*I can do*; self-efficacy), whereas the latter reflects a statement of intention and confidence in the given situation (*I will do*; pre-task confidence; cf. Bandura, 1986, 2006). Hence, while one may feel competent in a given task, one may still not expect to do well in imminent performance due to specific factors (e.g., feeling tired, low motivation). A more stable, yet less task-specific version of this creative self-belief is called *creative self-concept* and refers to the general appraisal of one's own creative competencies (Karwowski, Lebuda, & Beghetto, 2019). Personal knowledge, knowledge about the self, was also part of Flavell's (1979) conceptualization of metacognition. It describes inter- and intrapersonal differences in information about one's abilities in comparison to different areas or other people. Following the

argumentation from educational psychology, self-beliefs can be seen as so-called “hot knowledge” linked to motivational dimensions, but not “cold” information about cognition. Hence, while creative self-beliefs are predictive of creative performance, they do not represent metacognitive knowledge in a strict sense (Pintrich et al., 2000).

3.3. A dynamic conception of creative metacognition

The presented CMC framework illustrates the main components of creative metacognition and the relation between them. Importantly, these components are thought to be recruited and updated dynamically across creative task performance. People continually—during and after performing the task—adapt their mental representation of the process and adjust their cognitive actions accordingly, and experiences during task performance increase their task-related knowledge (see Ackerman, 2019; Rubenstein et al., 2018). To further illustrate the diverse, dynamic involvement of metacognitive components across the creative process, we exemplify it in the context of creative ideation. While the creative process and related metacognitive activities are generally assumed to exhibit a recursive, iterative character (Beghetto & Corazza, 2019; Botella et al., 2018; Glaveanu et al., 2013), we focus on three distinct stages relative to task performance (pre-task, during-task, and post-task), and at each stage describe the assumed core cognitive processes (CCPs) and metacognitive processes (MCP) involving MC control, monitoring, and knowledge (see Figure 2).

		Pre-task	During task	Post-task
CORE COGNITION	CREATIVE THINKING	Process task instructions	Core task (e.g., idea generation)	Presentation/implementation of solution
	METACOGNITIVE CONTROL	T P R Start task, or gather more info	Decision on task disengagement Select, change, devise strategy Report, elaborate, or dismiss response	Selection of responses
	METACOGNITIVE MONITORING	T P R Evaluation of task characteristics Anticipation of own performance (pre-task confidence) Evaluate examples	Reconsider task characteristics Evaluation of ongoing performance Evaluation of candidate responses	Update task characteristics Evaluation of own total performance (post-task confidence) Evaluation of own idea set
METACOGNITIVE KNOWLEDGE	T P R Activation of metacognitive knowledge	Retrieval of metacognitive knowledge	Update of metacognitive knowledge	

Figure 2.

A dynamic conception of creative metacognition (CMC) exemplified in the context of creative ideation. The figure gives an overview of relevant core cognitive processes and metacognitive processes, for the three CMC components of metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control across pre-, during-, and post-task stages. Note: T refers to task level; P refers to performance level; R refers to response level.

In the *pre-task stage* of creative ideation, one reads and interprets the task instructions (CCP), which implies building a problem representation, making it possible to define the problem (e.g., in the alternate uses task: “generate alternative uses for the object X”) and to identify task goals (e.g., “be creative/be fluent”; “consider or avoid the given examples”). This process is supported by activation of metacognitive knowledge, involving information from previous experience with this or similar tasks (mainly declarative MC knowledge). Based on this information, the task is evaluated (e.g., familiarity, difficulty) and anticipation of one’s own performance in this task is derived (MC monitoring). This evaluation informs the decision as to whether to engage in the task, or to dispose further resources for

task preparation (for example, studying task instructions and potential examples in more detail or looking for additional information; MC control).

During the task, the core cognitive processes are concerned with generating candidate ideas (i.e., searching and combining problem-relevant knowledge elements in new and effective ways). This involves retrieval of MC knowledge on how to approach this task, namely what strategy to employ and how to implement it most effectively (mainly procedural MC knowledge). The selected strategy closely guides specific cognitive operations during idea generation (CCP). For example, in the alternate uses task, following the *memory strategy*, people would attempt to recall previous solutions to similar problems, whereas following the *disassembly strategy*, they would imagine deconstructing the object and constructing novel uses from object parts (Gilhooly et al., 2007). Once the CCP yields candidate responses, they will be subjected to evaluation with respect to task goals (MC monitoring; i.e., is it a novel and effective use of the object?); this also implies identifying whether the idea is the same or very similar to previously reported responses and thus should be inhibited to avoid perseveration (Benedek, Franz et al., 2012). Discernment of ideas is supported by valid creativity conceptions including conditional knowledge about social expectations and display circumstances (MC knowledge; knowing what is deemed creative by others; e.g., would unethical or bizarre ideas be appreciated in this context?; e.g., Lebuda et al., 2021). Depending on this evaluation, one can decide on whether to report the idea or further elaborate on it, or (if it is too poorly evaluated) potentially dismiss it (MC control) altogether. During the task, ongoing task performance is constantly evaluated (e.g., I have many good ideas; see Berg, 2019), which recalibrates general judgments of task difficulty and confidence in one's own performance (MC monitoring). Once this monitoring of task performance signals that task performance is below one's expectations, it may initiate the reconsideration of the current strategy to adjust task performance to current needs (MC control). This regulation may involve selection of a different known strategy (involving MC knowledge) or spending time on finding a new, more effective task strategy (MC

control). If none of these options appear fruitful, one may eventually decide to abort the task (MC control).

At the *post-task stage*, one may proceed to present one's best ideas and to implement them (CCP). To this end, the full set of ideas will be reviewed for creativity (MC monitoring), allowing to rank responses or select a given number of most creative ones (MC control; Benedek et al., 2013; Silvia et al., 2008). Finally, one can evaluate one's total performance and overall task characteristics retrospectively (Pretz & McCollum, 2014) and conclude what strategies turned out to be more versus less effective (MC monitoring), leading to a recalibration of one's confidence with the task and an update of task-related knowledge (MC knowledge). This example illustrates the possible dynamic interactions between core- and metacognitive components involved in creative performance across pre-task, during task, and post-task stages. While we have chosen creative ideation for this example, similar time dynamics are expected to take place for other forms of creative cognition (such as creative problem solving) as well as applied performances (such as creative design, see Gero & Neill, 1998).

Scholars have become increasingly interested in time dynamics and variability of creative thinking processes within task and more broadly within person (Barbot, 2022; Corazza et al., 2022; Rominger et al., in press). Traditional single assessment designs have been extended to study pre-post or pre-during-post task changes, for instance, showing how confidence gets calibrated with respect to performance feedback over time (e.g., Karwowski et al., 2020). In a similar way, people have been asked to anticipate or reflect on task performance in a more time-sensitive way (e.g., consider five time periods within the task; Lucas & Nordgren, 2020). Think aloud protocols represent a more direct approach to examine ongoing thinking processes and have shed light on the type and prevalence of specific tasks strategies in creative ideation and creative problem solving (Fleck & Weisberg, 2004; Gilhooly et al., 2007; Pringle & Sowden, 2017; Smith & Vul, 2013). While they offer particularly intimate

qualitative insights, findings depend on people's reflection capacity and thus are moderated by their metacognitive skills. More generally, verbalizing thoughts and especially reflecting on questions during task performance can interfere with the main task by causing verbal overshadowing and eliciting additional metacognitive processes. Therefore, further approaches attempted to gain time-critical information in an unobtrusive way, such as from detailed analyses of performance dynamics (e.g., trends in fluency/originality; exploration/exploitation phases), post-hoc response classifications (e.g., old/new, and psychophysiological assessments). For example, Barbot was able to distinguish phases of exploration, production, and verification based on analyses of drawing behavior in a visual ideation task (Barbot, 2018). Jankowska and colleagues (2018) used eye-tracking and think aloud to distinguish phases including exploration, planning, reporting, and control within a visual ideation task. Finally, neuroscience methods (mainly EEG and fMRI; Benedek et al., 2019) have been used to investigate the neurocognitive mechanisms that underly specific phases and events in the creative process (generation vs. evaluation; Benedek, 2018; Ellamil et al., 2012; Kleinmintz et al., 2019; clustering vs. switching; Boot et al., 2017; Mastria et al., 2021; Ovando-Tellez et al., 2022; cognitive fixation; Camarda et al., 2018; Frith et al., 2022). For instance, switching and exploration behavior (flexibility pathway) is assumed to be supported by moderate levels of striatal dopamine, whereas more systematic processing and exploitation behavior (persistence pathway) are supported by moderate levels of prefrontal dopamine (Boot et al., 2017). Similarly, brain activation and connectivity changes over time on task can inform about time dynamics of cognitive processes. For example, increases of posterior EEG alpha activity have been interpreted in terms of increased top-down control and internal attention focus (Fink & Benedek, 2014), which appear especially associated with initial phases of reflection and late phases of mental simulations during idea evaluation (Rominger et al., 2019). Moreover, increased coupling between the default and executive control network in later stages of the task appear to reflect response evaluation processes (Beatty et al.,

2015). Hence, time-critical assessments of performance-related data across different modalities can be leveraged to explore the time dynamics that underly creative cognition in more detail.

4. Conclusions and future directions

A full appreciation of creative cognition includes an understanding of how people reflect on and regulate their own creative thinking processes. So far, little research has explicitly focused on creative metacognition, which may be partly due to the lack of a clear theoretical foundation regarding the role of metacognitive processes in creative cognition. Therefore, based on a review of the literature on various fields and traditions of psychology, we devised a systematic framework of creative metacognition that extends available theorizing in several ways. First, compared to existing models of the creative process (Lubart, 2001; Mumford et al., 2012), it distinguishes core and metacognitive processes and describes how they interact in creative performance. This distinction further implies different routes of how cognitive abilities can contribute to creative performance. It is supported by research showing double dissociation between core and metacognitive processes (Sidi et al., 2020). Second, while available models of metacognition mostly focused on convergent thinking tasks that have correct solutions (e.g., reasoning; Ackerman, & Thompson, 2017), the proposed framework focuses on divergent thinking (viz., creative ideation), a central aspect of creative cognition. High inherent uncertainty in creative ideation associated with navigating an open solution space, and evaluating solutions of varying quality implies unique challenges to metacognitive control and monitoring that warrant a focused investigation of metacognition in creativity. Third, the proposed framework not only considers dynamic aspects of metacognition (i.e., monitoring and control), but also a static part of metacognitive knowledge. Metacognitive knowledge is known to inform monitoring and control in creative cognition (e.g., Lucas, & Nordgren, 2020), but it is often inaccurate and potentially biased, which may undermine creative performance (Baas et al., 2015; Benedek et al., 2021). We argue that metacognitive knowledge is also substantially related to, yet separable from creative self-beliefs that

typically have a broader scope beyond the task at hand. Finally, compared to an initial conceptualization of creative metacognition that involved aspects of creative self-regulation (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2013), the present framework focused on describing the structure, function, and interaction of task-related (meta)cognitive processes. The resulting CMC framework is systematic in describing the role of established metacognitive components (control, monitoring, knowledge) and even distinguishes relevant subprocesses at three levels of granularity (i.e., levels of task, performance, and response). This additional differentiation allows us to further organize processes within each metacognitive component and thereby reconcile potentially conflicting findings such as over- and underestimation at the levels of performance versus responses (Pesout & Nietfeld, 2021; Sidi et al., 2020). The CMC framework is also dynamic in describing the assumed interplay between each metacognitive component across task performance (pre-, during-, post-task). This systematic, dynamic perspective appears to be a powerful approach for studying metacognition in complex cognitive activities, such as creative cognition. We thus hope that the presented framework facilitates systematic research on creative metacognition and potentially beyond.

While assumptions made in this framework were guided by available theory and research, many of them await more comprehensive empirical examination. Our review of relevant empirical work for each component and level highlighted areas of high interest (e.g., monitoring at response level) as well as potential gaps in the literature (e.g., knowledge at task level). These works also showcase various clever methods to be adopted and combined for a powerful future study of metacognitive processes in creativity, including think-aloud methods (Gilhooly et al., 2007; Pringle & Sowden, 2017), analyses of response behavior dynamics (Barbot, 2022; Corazza et al., 2022; Rominger et al., in press), pre-, during-, and post-task reflections on monitoring and control activities (Karwowski, Han, & Beghetto, 2019; Puente-Diaz, Cavazos-Arroyo, & Vargas-Barrera, 2021), as well as the assessment of neurophysiological indicators of cognitive processes and performance-related events (Beatty et al., 2016; Benedek et al.,

2019; Jia et al., 2019; Rominger et al., 2022; Stevens & Zabelina, 2019; Walcher et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2020).

One particularly important goal for future research is to identify the unique contributions of cognitive control in core cognitive and metacognitive processes. Research of the last few decades has revealed robust associations between creative performance and executive control as well as intelligence (for reviews and meta-analyses, see Benedek & Jauk, 2018, 2019; Gerwig et al., 2021), but associations with creative performance could be due to cognitive control supporting either core or metacognitive cognitive processes, or both. For example, higher cognitive ability may support more accurate decisions when selecting responses and strategies, but it could also support more effective implementation of any given strategy. Indeed, initial works found that cognitive ability is related to higher accuracy in judging own ideas (Benedek et al., 2016; Karwowski et al., 2020) as well as more effective strategy use (Gilhooly et al., 2007; Nusbaum et al., 2014). Further evidence indicated that cognitive control can also be detrimental to creative performance under specific circumstances (Chrysikou, 2019; Zabelina, 2018). In fact, metacognitive processes can be biased by simplistic heuristics (Ackerman, 2019) and interfere with resources needed for skilled task execution (e.g., DeCaro et al., 2011). Dual-process models of creativity (Benedek & Jauk, 2018; Chrysikou, 2018; Sowden et al., 2015) assume that creative cognition involves both spontaneous and controlled forms of thinking (Type 1 and 2 processes). Considering the role of metacognition, it has typically been viewed as a mostly deliberate, cognitively demanding process (Type 2; e.g. Stanovich, 2012), yet some accounts also propose to distinguish dual-processes (Type 1 and 2) within metacognition (see Shea et al., 2014). Future research is thus challenged to examine in more detail how cognitive control supports—and potentially constraints—creative task performance via core cognitive and metacognitive processes.

The CMC framework considers metacognitive knowledge besides problem-relevant knowledge, which extends classical conceptions of the role of memory in creative cognition: While memory, of course, provides relevant semantic and episodic information to forge new ideas and solve creative problems (Abraham & Bubic, 2015; Beaty & Schacter, 2018; Kenett & Faust, 2019; Yang et al., 2022), it also offers metacognitive knowledge (declarative and procedural; Mumford et al., 2012) supporting more accurate MC monitoring and MC control. Recent theorizing outlined different ways of how memory can contribute to idea generation and evaluation, and thus to core and metacognitive processes (Benedek et al., in press). Specifically, it assumes that the generation of candidate ideas relies on search and reconstruction of (problem-relevant) semantic and episodic memory elements, whereas in idea evaluation, memory is assumed to assess idea novelty relative to available experience and to assess idea effectiveness by means of mental simulations supported by semantic knowledge and episodic simulation mechanisms. This raises the question of how individual differences in knowledge, such as higher experience and domain-specific creative expertise, but also inaccurate beliefs and biases, affect creative performance by (mis)informing relevant monitoring and control processes.

The present framework of creative metacognition provides a conceptual basis to distinguish between core cognitive and metacognitive processes in creative cognition, distinguishes central components of metacognition at different levels of granularity, and describes their dynamics over time. We hope that the theoretical formalizations provided by this framework will guide and facilitate future systematic research towards a more comprehensive understanding of creative cognition.

References

- Abraham, A., & Bubic, A. (2015). Semantic memory as the root of imagination. *Frontiers in Psychology, 6*.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00325>
- Acar, S., Runco, M. A., & Park, H. (2020). What should people be told when they take a divergent thinking test? A meta-analytic review of explicit instructions for divergent thinking. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 14*(1), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000256>
- Ackerman, R. (2014). The diminishing criterion model for metacognitive regulation of time investment. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General, 143*(3), 1349–1368.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035098>
- Ackerman, R. (2019). Heuristic cues for meta-reasoning judgments: Review and methodology. *Psihologijske Teme, 28*(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.31820/pt.28.1.1>
- Ackerman, R., & Beller, Y. (2017). Shared and distinct cue utilization for metacognitive judgments during reasoning and memorization. *Thinking & Reasoning, 23*(4), 376–408.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13546783.2017.1328373>
- Ackerman, R., & Thompson, V. A. (2017). Meta-Reasoning: Monitoring and control of thinking and reasoning. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 21*(8), 607–617. Doi: 10.1016/j.tics.2017.05.004
- Agogu, M., Kazaki, A., Hatchuel, A., Le Masson, P., Weil, B., Poirel, N., & Cassotti, M. (2014). The impact of type of examples on originality: explaining fixation and stimulation effects. *The Journal of Creative Behavior, 48*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.37>
- Anderson, R. C., & Haney, M. (2021). Reflection in the creative process of early adolescents: The mediating roles of creative metacognition, self-efficacy, and self-concept. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 15*(4), 612–626. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000324>
- Antonietti, A., Ignazi, S., & Perego, P. (2000). Metacognitive knowledge about problem-solving methods. *British Journal of Educational Psychology, 70*(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709900157921>

- Armbruster, B. B. (1989). Metacognition in creativity. In J. A. Glorver, R. R. Ronning, & C. R. Reynolds (Eds.), *Handbook of creativity* (pp. 177–182). Plenum.
- Baas, M., Koch, S., Nijstad, B. A., & De Dreu, C. K. W. (2015). Conceiving creativity: The nature and consequences of laypeople's beliefs about the realization of creativity. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 9(3), 340–354. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0039420>
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Bandura, A. (2006). Guide to construction of self-efficacy scales. In F. Pajares & T. Urdan (Eds.), *Self-efficacy beliefs of adolescents* (Vol. 5, pp. 307–337). Information Age.
- Barbot, B. (2018). The dynamics of creative ideation: Introducing a new assessment paradigm. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2529. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02529>
- Barbot, B. (2022). Intra-individual variability in creativity: Nature, measurement, and prospects. *European Psychologist*. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000470>
- Beaty, R. E., Benedek, M., Kaufman, S. B., & Silvia, P. J. (2015). Default and executive network coupling supports creative idea production. *Scientific Reports*, 5(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep10964>
- Beaty, R. E., Benedek, M., Silvia, P. J., & Schacter, D. L. (2016). Creative cognition and brain network dynamics. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 20(2), 87-95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.10.004>
- Beaty, R. E., Christensen, A. P., Benedek, M., Silvia, P. J., & Schacter, D. L. (2017). Creative constraints: Brain activity and network dynamics underlying semantic interference during idea production. *NeuroImage*, 148, 189-196. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.01.012
- Beaty, R. E., & Schacter, D. L. (2018). Episodic memory and cognitive control: Contributions to creative idea production. In R. E. Jung & O. Vartanian (eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of the neuroscience of creativity* (pp. 249-260). Cambridge University Press.
- Beaty, R. E., & Silvia, P. J. (2012). Why do ideas get more creative across time? An executive

- interpretation of the serial order effect in divergent thinking tasks. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 6(4), 309–319. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029171>
- Beghetto, R. A., & Corazza, G. E. (Eds.). (2019). *Dynamic perspectives on creativity: New directions for theory, research, and practice in education* (Vol. 4). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99163-4>
- Beghetto, R. A., & Karwowski, M. (2017). Toward untangling creative self-beliefs. In M. Karwowski & J. C. Kaufman (Eds.), *The creative self: Effects of self-efficacy, mindset and identity* (pp. 4–24). Academic Press.
- Benedek, M. (2018). The neuroscience of creative idea generation. In Kapoula, Z., Renoult, J., Volle, E., & Andreatta, M. (Eds.), *Exploring transdisciplinarity in art and science* (pp. 31-48). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland AG. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-76054-4
- Benedek, M., Beaty, R. E., Schacter, D. L., & Kenett, Y. N. (in press). The role of memory in creative ideation. Article accepted in principle in *Nature Reviews Psychology*.
- Benedek, M., Christensen, A. P., Fink, A., & Beaty, R. E. (2019). Creativity assessment in neuroscience research. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 13(2), 218–226. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000215>
- Benedek, M., & Fink, A. (2019). Toward a neurocognitive framework of creative cognition: The role of memory, attention, and cognitive control. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 27, 116–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2018.11.002>
- Benedek, M., Franz, F., Heene, M., & Neubauer, A. C. (2012). Differential effects of cognitive inhibition and intelligence on creativity. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 53(4), 480–485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.04.014>
- Benedek, M., & Jauk, E. (2018). Spontaneous and controlled processes in creative cognition. In Fox, K. C. R. & Christoff, K. (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Spontaneous Thought: Mind-Wandering*,

Creativity, and Dreaming (pp. 285-298). Oxford University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190464745.013.22>

Benedek, M., & Jauk, E. (2019). Creativity and cognitive control. In J. C. Kaufman & R. J. Sternberg (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of creativity* (pp. 200–223). Cambridge University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316979839.012>

Benedek, M., Jauk, E., Sommer, M., Arendasy, M., & Neubauer, A. C. (2014). Intelligence, creativity, and cognitive control: The common and differential involvement of executive functions in intelligence and creativity. *Intelligence*, *46*, 73–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2014.05.007>

Benedek, M., Karstendiek, M., Ceh, S. M., Grabner, R. H., Krammer, G., Lebuda, I., Silvia, P. J., Cotter, K. N., Li, Y., Hu, W., Martskvishvili, K., & Kaufman, J. C. (2021). Creativity myths: Prevalence and correlates of misconceptions on creativity. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *182*, 111068.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111068>

Benedek, M., Könen, T., & Neubauer, A. C. (2012). Associative abilities underlying creativity. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *6*(3), 273-281. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027059>

Benedek, M., Mühlmann, C., Jauk, E., & Neubauer, A. C. (2013). Assessment of divergent thinking by means of the subjective top-scoring method: Effects of the number of top-ideas and time-on-task on reliability and validity. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *7*(4), 341–349. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033644>

Benedek, M., Nordtvedt, N., Jauk, E., Koschmieder, C., Pretsch, J., Krammer, G., & Neubauer, A. C. (2016). Assessment of creativity evaluation skills: A psychometric investigation in prospective teachers. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, *21*, 75–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2016.05.007>

Benedek, M., Schües, T., Beaty, R. E., Jauk, E., Koschutnig, K., Fink, A., & Neubauer, A. C. (2018). To create or to recall original ideas: Brain processes associated with the imagination of novel object uses. *Cortex*, *99*, 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2017.10.024>

- Berg, J. M. (2019). When silver is gold: Forecasting the potential creativity of initial ideas. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 154, 96-117.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2019.08.004>
- Boot, N., Baas, M., Van Gaal, S., Cools, R., & De Dreu, C. K. W. (2017). Creative cognition and dopaminergic modulation of fronto-striatal networks: Integrative review and research agenda. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 78, 13–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2017.04.007>
- Botella, M., Zenasni, F., & Lubart, T. (2018). What are the stages of the creative process? What visual art students are saying. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2266. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02266>
- Camarda, A., Salvia, E., Vidal, J., Weil, B., Poirel, N., Houde, O., ... & Cassotti, M. (2018). Neural basis of functional fixedness during creative idea generation: an EEG study. *Neuropsychologia*, 118, 4-12.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2018.03.009>
- Campbell, D. T. (1960). Blind variation and selective retentions in creative thought as in other knowledge processes. *Psychological Review*, 67(6), 380. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0040373>
- Ceh, S. M., Edelman, C., Hofer, G., & Benedek, M. (2022). Assessing raters: What factors predict discernment in novice creativity raters? *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 56 (1), 41-54
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.515>
- Chrysikou, E. G. (2018). The costs and benefits of cognitive control for creativity. In R. E. Jung & O. Vartanian (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of the neuroscience of creativity* (pp. 299–317). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316556238.018>
- Chrysikou, E. G. (2019). Creativity in and out of (cognitive) control. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 27, 94–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2018.09.014>
- Chrysikou, E. G., Motyka, K., Nigro, C., Yang, S.-I., & Thompson-Schill, S. L. (2016). Functional fixedness in creative thinking tasks depends on stimulus modality. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the*

Arts, 10(4), 425–435. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000050>

- Corazza, G. E., Agnoli, S., & Mastria, S. (2022). The dynamic creativity framework: Theoretical and empirical investigations. *European Psychologist*. Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000473>
- Danek, A. H., & Wiley, J. (2020). What causes the insight memory advantage? *Cognition*, 205, 104411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2020.104411>
- Danek, A. H., Wiley, J., & Öllinger, M. (2016). Solving classical insight problems without Aha! Experience: 9 dot, 8 coin, and matchstick arithmetic problems. *The Journal of Problem Solving*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.7771/1932-6246.1183>
- Davidson, J. E., Deuser, R., & Sternberg, R. J. (1994). The role of metacognition in problem solving. In J. Metcalfe & A. P. Shimamura (Eds.), *Metacognition: Knowing about knowing* (pp. 207–226). The MIT Press.
- Davidson, J. E., & Sternberg, R. (1998). Smart problem solving: How metacognition helps. In D. J. Hacker, A. C. Graesser, & J. Dunlosky (Eds.), *Metacognition in educational theory and practice* (pp. 47–69). Lawrence Erlbaum.
- DeCaro, M. S., Thomas, R. D., Albert, N. B., & Beilock, S. L. (2011). Choking under pressure: Multiple routes to skill failure. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 140(3), 390–406. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023466>
- De Dreu, C. K. W., Baas, M., & Nijstad, B. A. (2008). Hedonic tone and activation level in the mood-creativity link: Toward a dual pathway to creativity model. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 94(5), 739–756. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.94.5.739>
- Diedrich, J., Benedek, M., Jauk, E., & Neubauer, A. C. (2015). Are creative ideas novel and useful? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 9(1), 35. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000137>
- Dinsmore, D. L., Alexander, P. A., & Loughlin, S. M. (2008). Focusing the conceptual lens on

- metacognition, self-regulation, and self-regulated learning. *Educational Psychology Review*, 20(4), 391–409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-008-9083-6>
- Donzallaz, M. C., Haaf, J. M., & Stevenson, C. (2021). *Creative or not? Hierarchical diffusion modeling of the creative evaluation process* [Preprint]. PsyArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/5eryv>
- Duncker, K. (1945). On problem solving. *Psychological Monographs*, 58(5), i–113. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0093599>
- Dunlosky, J., & Rawson, K. A. (2012). Overconfidence produces underachievement: Inaccurate self-evaluations undermine students' learning and retention. *Learning and Instruction*, 22(4), 271–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2011.08.003>
- Efklides, A. (2006). Metacognition and affect: What can metacognitive experiences tell us about the learning process? *Educational Research Review*, 1(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2005.11.001>
- Efklides, A. (2011). Interactions of metacognition with motivation and affect in self-regulated learning: The MASRL model. *Educational Psychologist*, 46(1), 6–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.538645>
- Ellamil, M., Dobson, C., Beeman, M., & Christoff, K. (2012). Evaluative and generative modes of thought during the creative process. *Neuroimage*, 59, 1783–1794. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2011.08.008
- Evans, J. St. B. T., & Stanovich, K. E. (2013). Dual-process theories of higher cognition: Advancing the debate. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 8, 223–241. doi: 10.1177/1745691612460685
- Fayena-Tawil, F., Kozbelt, A., & Sitaras, L. (2011). Think global, act local: A protocol analysis comparison of artists' and nonartists' cognitions, metacognitions, and evaluations while drawing. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 5(2), 135–145. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021019>
- Fink, A., & Benedek, M. (2014). EEG alpha power and creative ideation. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 44, 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.12.002>

- Finke, R. A. (1996). Imagery, creativity, and emergent structure. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 5, 381–393. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027373>
- Finke, R. A., Ward, T. B., & Smith, S. S. (1992). *Creative cognition: Theory, research, and applications*. MIT Press.
- Flavell, J. H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new areas of cognitive-developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34, 906–911. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.34.10.906>
- Fleck, J. I., & Weisberg, R. W. (2004). The use of verbal protocols as data: An analysis of insight in the candle problem. *Memory & Cognition*, 32(6), 990–1006. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196876>
- Fleming, S. M., & Daw, N. D. (2017). Self-evaluation of decision-making: A general Bayesian framework for metacognitive computation. *Psychological Review*, 124(1), 91–114. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000045>
- Forthmann, B., Gerwig, A., Holling, H., Çelik, P., Storme, M., & Lubart, T. (2016). The be-creative effect in divergent thinking: The interplay of instruction and object frequency. *Intelligence*, 57, 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2016.03.005>
- Forthmann, B., Szardenings, C., & Holling, H. (2020). Understanding the confounding effect of fluency in divergent thinking scores: Revisiting average scores to quantify artifactual correlation. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 14(1), 94–112. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000196>
- Forthmann, B., Wilken, A., Doeblner, P., & Holling, H. (2019). Strategy induction enhances creativity in figural divergent thinking. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 53(1), 18–29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.159>
- Frazier, L. D., Schwartz, B. L., & Metcalfe, J. (2021). The MAPS model of self-regulation: Integrating metacognition, agency, and possible selves. *Metacognition and Learning*, 16(2), 297–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-020-09255-3>
- Frith, E., Gerver, C. R., Benedek, M., Christensen, A. P., & Beaty, R. E. (2022). Neural representations of

- conceptual fixation during creative imagination. *Creativity Research Journal*, 34(1), 106-122.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2021.2008699>
- George, T., & Mielicki, M. K. (2022). Bullshit receptivity, problem solving, and metacognition: Simply the BS, not better than all the rest. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 1–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13546783.2022.2066724>
- George, T., Mielicki, M. K., & Wiley, J. (2021). Great expectations: Misleading effects of images in the alternate uses task. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000380>
- George, T., & Wiley, J. (2020). Need something different? Here's what's been done: Effects of examples and task instructions on creative idea generation. *Memory & Cognition*, 48(2), 226–243.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-019-01005-4>
- George, T., Wiley, J., Koppel, R. H., & Storm, B. C. (2019). Constraining or constructive? The effects of examples on idea novelty. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 53(3), 396-403.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.178>
- Gero, J. S., & Mc Neill, T. (1998). An approach to the analysis of design protocols. *Design studies*, 19(1), 21-61. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(97\)00015-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(97)00015-X)
- Gerwig, A., Miroshnik, K., Forthmann, B., Benedek, M., Karwowski, M., & Holling, H. (2021). The relationship between intelligence and divergent thinking – a meta-analytic update. *Journal of Intelligence*, 9(2), 23; <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence9020023>
- Gilhooly, K. J., Fioratou, E., Anthony, S. H., & Wynn, V. (2007). Divergent thinking: Strategies and executive involvement in generating novel uses for familiar objects. *British Journal of Psychology*, 98(4), 611–625. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.2007.tb00467.x>
- Gilhooly, K. J., & Murphy, P. (2005). Differentiating insight from non-insight problems. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 11(3), 279-302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546780442000187>

- Glaveanu, V. P., Hanchett Hanson, M., Baer, J., Barbot, B., Clapp, E. P., Corazza, G. E., ... & Sternberg, R. J. (2020). Advancing creativity theory and research: A socio-cultural manifesto. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 54(3), 741-745. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.395>
- Glaveanu, V., Lubart, T., Bonnardel, N., Botella, M., Biais, P.-M. de, Desainte-Catherine, M., Georgsdottir, A., Guillou, K., Kurtag, G., Mouchiroud, C., Storme, M., Wojtczuk, A., & Zenasni, F. (2013). Creativity as action: Findings from five creative domains. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00176>
- Grohman, M., Wodniecka, Z., & Klusak, M. (2006). Divergent thinking and evaluation skills: do they always go together? *Journal of Creative Behavior*, 40(2), 125–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2162-6057.2006.tb01269.x>
- Guo, Y., Lin, S., Acar, S., Jin, S., Xu, X., Feng, Y., & Zeng, Y. (2022). Divergent thinking and evaluative skill: A meta-analysis. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, jocb.539. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.539>
- Hao, N., Ku, Y., Liu, M., Hu, Y., Bodner, M., Grabner, R. H., et al. (2016). Reflection enhances creativity: beneficial effects of idea evaluation on idea generation. *Brain and Cognition*, 10330–10337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2016.01.005>.
- Hargrove, R. A., & Nietfeld, J. L. (2015). The Impact of metacognitive instruction on creative problem solving. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 83(3), 291–318.
- Harrington, D. M. (1975). Effects of explicit instructions to “be creative” on the psychological meaning of divergent thinking test scores. *Journal of Personality*, 43(3), 434–454. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1975.tb00715.x>
- Hart, Y., Goldberg, H., Striem-Amit, E., Mayo, A. E., Noy, L., & Alon, U. (2018). Creative exploration as a scale-invariant search on a meaning landscape. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 5411. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07715-8>
- Hart, Y., Kosoy, E., Liquin, E. G., Leonard, J. A., Mackey, A. P., & Gopnik, A. (2022). The development of

creative search strategies. *Cognition*, 225, 105102.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105102>

Hart, Y., Mayo, A. E., Mayo, R., Rozenkrantz, L., Tendler, A., Alon, U., & Noy, L. (2017). Creative foraging: An experimental paradigm for studying exploration and discovery. *PLOS ONE*, 12(8), e0182133.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182133>

Hass, R. W. (2017). Semantic search during divergent thinking. *Cognition*, 166, 344–357.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2017.05.039>

Hills, T. T., Jones, M. N., & Todd, P. M. (2012). Optimal foraging in semantic memory. *Psychological Review*, 119(2), 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027373>

Hofer, G., Macher, S., & Neubauer, A. C. (2022). Love is not blind: What romantic partners know about our abilities compared to ourselves, our close friends, and our acquaintances. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 98, 104211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2022.104211>

Hommel, B. (2015). Between persistence and flexibility: The Yin and Yang of action control. In: A.J. Elliot (Ed.), *Advances in motivation science, Vol. 2* (pp. 33-67). New York: Elsevier.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/bs.adms.2015.04.003>

Horn, C., Bruning, R., Schraw, G., & Curry, E. (1993). Paths to success in the college classroom. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 18(4), 464–478.

<https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1993.1035>

Ivcevic, Z., & Nusbaum, E. C. (2017). From having an idea to doing something with it: Self-regulation for creativity. In M. Karwowski, & J. C. Kaufman (Eds.), *The creative self: Effects of beliefs, self-efficacy, mindset, and identity* (pp. 343–365). Academic Press.

Jankowska, D. M., Czerwonka, M., Lebuda, I., & Karwowski, M. (2018). Exploring the creative process: integrating psychometric and eye-tracking approaches. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1931.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01931>

- Jia, X., Li, W., & Cao, L. (2019). The role of metacognitive components in creative thinking. *Frontiers in Psychology, 10*, 2404. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02404>
- Kaplan, A. (2008). Clarifying metacognition, self-regulation, and self-regulated learning: What's the purpose? *Educational Psychology Review, 20*(4), 477–484. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-008-9087-2>
- Karwowski, M. (2014). Creative mindsets: Measurement, correlates, consequences. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 8*(1), 62–70. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034898>
- Karwowski, M. (2016). Culture and psychometric studies of creativity. In *The Palgrave handbook of creativity and culture research* (pp. 159-186). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Karwowski, M., & Beghetto, R. A. (2017). Toward untangling creative self-beliefs. In M. Karwowski, & J. C. Kaufman, (Eds.), *The creative self: Effects of self-efficacy, mindset and identity* (pp. 3-22). Academic Press.
- Karwowski, M., Czerwonka, M., & Kaufman, J. C. (2020). Does intelligence strengthen creative metacognition? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 14*(3), 353–360. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000208>
- Karwowski, M., Han, M.-H., & Beghetto, R. A. (2019). Toward dynamizing the measurement of creative confidence beliefs. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 13*(2), 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000229>
- Karwowski, M., & Kaufman, J. C. (Eds.). (2017). *The creative self*. Academic Press.
- Karwowski, M., Lebuda, I., & Beghetto, R. (2019). Creative self-beliefs. In J. Kaufman & R. Sternberg (Eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Creativity* (pp. 396-418). Cambridge University Press.
- Kaufman, J. C., & Beghetto, R. A. (2009). Beyond Big and little: The four C model of creativity. *Review of General Psychology, 13*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0013688>
- Kaufman, J. C., & Beghetto, R. A. (2013). In praise of Clark Kent: creative metacognition and the

importance of teaching kids when (not) to be creative. *Roeper Review*, 35(3), 155–165.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02783193.2013.799413>

Kaufman, J. C., Beghetto, R. A., & Watson, C. (2016). Creative metacognition and self-ratings of creative performance: A 4-C perspective. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 51, 394–399.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2015.05.004>

Kaufman, J. C., Pumacahua, T. T., & Holt, R. E. (2013). Personality and creativity in realistic, investigative, artistic, social, and enterprising college majors. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 54(8), 913–917. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2013.01.013>

Kenett, Y. N., & Faust, M. (2019). A semantic network cartography of the creative mind. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 23(4), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2019.01.007>

Kleinmintz, O. M., Goldstein, P., Mayseless, N., Abecasis, D., & Shamay-Tsoory, S. G. (2014). Expertise in musical improvisation and creativity: The mediation of idea evaluation. *PLoS ONE*, 9(7), e101568.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0101568>

Kleinmintz, O. M., Ivancovsky, T., & Shamay-Tsoory, S. G. (2019). The two-fold model of creativity: The neural underpinnings of the generation and evaluation of creative ideas. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 27, 131–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2018.11.004>

Koriat, A. (1993). How do we know that we know? The accessibility model of the feeling of knowing. *Psychological Review*, 100, 609–639.

Koriat, A. (1997). Monitoring one's own knowledge during study: A cue-utilization approach to judgments of learning. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 126(4), 349–370.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.126.4.349>

Koriat, A., & Levy-Sadot, R. (1999). Processes underlying metacognitive judgments: Information-based and experience-based monitoring of one's own knowledge. In S. Chaiken, & Y. Trope (Eds.), *Dual process theories in social psychology* (pp. 483–502). Guilford Press.

- Koriat, A., & Levy-Sadot, R. (2001). The combined contributions of the cue-familiarity and accessibility heuristics to feelings of knowing. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 27(1), 34–53. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.27.1.34>
- Koriat, A., Ma'ayan, H., & Nussinson, R. (2006). The intricate relationships between monitoring and control in metacognition: Lessons for the cause-and-effect relation between subjective experience and behavior. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 135(1), 36-68. doi: 10.1037/0096-3445.135.1.36
- Kozbelt, A. (2007). A quantitative analysis of Beethoven as self-critic: Implications for psychological theories of musical creativity. *Psychology of Music*, 35(1), 144–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735607068892>.
- Kruger, J., & Dunning, D. (1999). Unskilled and unaware of it: How difficulties in recognizing one's own incompetence lead to inflated self-assessments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77(6), 1121–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.77.6.1121>
- Kuhn, D. (2021). Metacognition matters in many ways. *Educational Psychologist*, 57(2), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2021.1988603>
- Lebuda, I., Figura, B., & Karwowski, M. (2021). Creativity and the Dark Triad: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 92, 104088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2021.104088>
- Lieder, F., & Griffiths, T. L. (2017). Strategy selection as rational metareasoning. *Psychological Review*, 124(6), 762–794. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/rev0000075>
- Lubart, T. I. (2001). Models of the creative process: Past, present and future. *Creativity Research Journal*, 13(3-4), 295-308. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326934CRJ1334_07
- Lucas, B. J., & Nordgren, L. F. (2015). People underestimate the value of persistence for creative performance. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 109(2), 232–243. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspa0000030>

- Lucas, B. J., & Nordgren, L. F. (2020). The creative cliff illusion. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *117*(33), 19830–19836. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2005620117>
- Malanchini, M., Engelhardt, L. E., Grotzinger, A. D., Harden, K. P., & Tucker-Drob, E. M. (2019). “Same but different”: Associations between multiple aspects of self-regulation, cognition, and academic abilities. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *117*(6), 1164–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000224>
- Marsh, R. L., Landau, J. D., & Hicks, J. L. (1996). How examples may (and may not) constrain creativity. *Memory & Cognition*, *24*(5), 669–680. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03201091>
- Mastria, S., Agnoli, S., Zanon, M., Acar, S., Runco, M. A., & Corazza, G. E. (2021). Clustering and switching in divergent thinking: Neurophysiological correlates underlying flexibility during idea generation. *Neuropsychologia*, *158*, 107890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2021.107890>
- Matheson, H. E., & Kenett, Y. N. (2021). A novel coding scheme for assessing responses in divergent thinking: An embodied approach. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *15*(3), 412–425. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000297>
- Mednick, S. A. (1962). The associative basis of the creative process. *Psychological Review*, *69*, 220–232. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0048850>
- Mehta, R., Zhu, R. (Juliet), & Cheema, A. (2012). Is noise always bad? Exploring the effects of ambient noise on creative cognition. *Journal of Consumer Research*, *39*(4), 784–799. <https://doi.org/10.1086/665048>
- Metcalfe, J. (1986). Feeling of knowing in memory and problem solving. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, *12*(2), 288–294. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.12.2.288>
- Metcalfe, J. (1998). Cognitive optimism: Self-deception or memory-based processing heuristics? *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, *2*(2), 100–110.

https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr0202_3

- Metcalfe, J., & Finn, B. (2008). Familiarity and retrieval processes in delayed judgments of learning. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, *34*, 1084-1097. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012580>
- Metcalfe, J., & Wiebe, D. (1987). Intuition in insight and noninsight problem solving. *Memory & Cognition*, *15*(3), 238–246. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03197722>
- Mumford, M. D., Medeiros, K. E., & Partlow, P. J. (2012). Creative thinking: Processes, strategies, and knowledge. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, *46*(1), 30–47. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.003>
- Müller, J. S., Melwani, S., & Goncalo, J. A. (2012). The bias against creativity: Why people desire but reject creative ideas. *Psychological Science*, *23*(1), 13-17.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09567976114210>
- Nelson, T. O. (1990). Metamemory: A theoretical framework and new findings. In *Psychology of Learning and Motivation* (Vol. 26, pp. 125–173). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0079-7421\(08\)60053-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0079-7421(08)60053-5)
- Nelson, T. O., & Narens, L. (1994). Why investigate metacognition? In J. Metcalfe & A. P. Shimamura (Eds.), *Metacognition: Knowing about knowing* (pp. 1–25). The MIT Press.
- Nietfeld, J. L., & Schraw, G. (2002). The effect of knowledge and strategy training on monitoring accuracy. *The Journal of Educational Research*, *95*(3), 131–142.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220670209596583>
- Nijstad, B. A., De Dreu, C. K. W., Rietzschel, E. F., & Baas, M. (2010). The dual pathway to creativity model: Creative ideation as a function of flexibility and persistence. *European Review of Social Psychology*, *21*(1), 34–77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10463281003765323>
- Norman, E., Pfuhl, G., Sæle, R. G., Svartdal, F., Låg, T., & Dahl, T. I. (2019). Metacognition in psychology. *Review of General Psychology*, *23*(4), 403–424. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1089268019883821>
- Nusbaum, E. C., & Silvia, P. J. (2011). Are intelligence and creativity really so different? Fluid intelligence,

executive processes, and strategy use in divergent thinking. *Intelligence*, 39(1), 36–45.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2010.11.002>

Nusbaum, E. C., Silvia, P. J., & Beaty, R. E. (2014). Ready, set, create: What instructing people to “be creative” reveals about the meaning and mechanisms of divergent thinking. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 8(4), 423–432. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036549>

O’Connor, A. J., Nemeth, C. J., & Akutsu, S. (2013). Consequences of beliefs about the malleability of creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, 25(2), 155–162.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2013.783739>

Ohlsson, S. (1992). Information processing explanations of insight and related phenomena. In M. T. Keane & K. J. Gilhooly (Eds.), *Advances in the psychology of thinking* (pp. 176–201). Harvester-Wheatsheaf. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.27.1.176>

Ovando-Tellez, M., Benedek, M., Kenett, Y. N., Hills, T., Bouanane, S., Bernard, M., Belo, J., Bieth, T., & Volle, E. (2022). An investigation of the cognitive and neural correlates of semantic memory search related to creative ability. *Communications Biology*, 5(1), 604.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-03547-x>

Pesout, O., & Nietfeld, J. L. (2021). How creative am I? Examining judgments and predictors of creative performance. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 40, 100836.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2021.100836>

Pesut, D. J. (1990). Creative thinking as a self-regulatory metacognitive process: A model for education, training and further research. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 24(2), 105–110.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2162-6057.1990.tb00532.x>

Pintrich, P. R., Wolters, C., & Baxter, G. P. (2000). Assessing metacognition and self-regulated learning. In G. Schraw & J. C. Ampara (Eds.), *Issues in the measurement of metacognition* (pp. 43-97).

University of Nebraska Press.

- Plucker, J. A., Runco, M. A., & Lim, W. (2006). Predicting ideational behavior from divergent thinking and discretionary time on task. *Creativity Research Journal*, *18*(1), 55–63.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326934crj1801_7
- Pretz, J. E., & McCollum, V. A. (2014). Self-perceptions of creativity do not always reflect actual creative performance. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *8*(2), 227–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035597>
- Pringle, A., & Sowden, P. T. (2017). Unearthing the creative thinking process: Fresh insights from a think-aloud study of garden design. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, *11*(3), 344–358.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000144>
- Puente-Diaz, R., & Cavazos-Arroyo, J. (2017). The influence of creative mindsets on achievement goals, enjoyment, creative self-efficacy and performance among business students. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, *24*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2017.02.007>
- Puente-Diaz, R., & Cavazos-Arroyo, J. (2020). Creative metacognitive feelings as a source of information for creative self-efficacy, creativity potential, intrapersonal idea selection, and task enjoyment. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, *54*(3), 499-507. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.384>
- Puente-Diaz, R., & Cavazos-Arroyo, J. (2021). Creative personal identity and creative mindsets, and their implications for creative potential and metacognition: A latent variable and a latent class approach. *Creativity. Theories – Research - Applications*, *8*(2), 20–31.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/ctra-2021-0015>
- Puente-Diaz, R., & Cavazos-Arroyo, J. (2022). Creative self-efficacy and metacognitive feelings as sources of information when generating, evaluating, and selecting creative ideas: A metacognitive perspective. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.557>
- Puente-Diaz, R., Cavazos-Arroyo, J., Puerta-Sierra, L., & Vargas-Barrera, F. (2022). The contribution Openness to Experience and its two aspects to the explanation of idea generation, evaluation and

selection: A metacognitive perspective. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 185, 111240.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111240>

Puente-Diaz, R., Cavazos-Arroyo, J., & Puerta-Sierra, L. (2021). Idea generation, selection, and evaluation: A metacognitive approach. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.505>

Puente-Diaz, R., Cavazos-Arroyo, J., & Vargas-Barrera, F. (2021). Metacognitive feelings as a source of information in the evaluation and selection of creative ideas. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 39, 100767. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2020.100767>

Reiter-Palmon, R., Forthmann, B., & Barbot, B. (2019). Scoring divergent thinking tests: A review and systematic framework. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 13(2), 144–152.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000227>

Rietzschel, E. F., Nijstad, B. A., & Stroebe, W. (2010). The selection of creative ideas after individual idea generation: Choosing between creativity and impact. *British Journal of Psychology*, 101(1), 47–68.

<https://doi.org/10.1348/000712609X414204>

Rominger, C., Benedek, M., Lebeda, I., Perchtold-Stefan, C. M., Schwerdtfeger, A. R., Papousek, I., & Fink, A. (2022). Functional brain activation patterns of creative metacognitive monitoring. *Neuropsychologia*, 177, 108416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2022.108416>

Rominger, C., Papousek, I., Perchtold, C. M., Benedek, M., Weiss, E. M., Schwerdtfeger, A., & Fink, A. (2019). Creativity is associated with a characteristic U-shaped function of alpha power changes accompanied by an early increase in functional coupling. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience*, 19(4), 1012-1021. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13415-019-00699-y>

Rominger, C., Schwerdtfeger, A. R., Benedek, M., Perchtold-Stefan, C. M., & Fink, A. (in press). Ecological momentary assessment of creative ideation. *European Psychologist*.

<https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000471>

- Rubenstein, L. D., Callan, G. L., & Ridgley, L. M. (2018). Anchoring the creative process within a self-regulated learning framework: Inspiring assessment methods and future research. *Educational Psychology Review, 30*(3), 921–945. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-017-9431-5>
- Runco, M. A., & Acar, S. (2010). Do tests of divergent thinking have an experiential bias? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 4*(3), 144–148. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018969>
- Runco, M. A., & Smith, W. R. (1992). Interpersonal and intrapersonal evaluations of creative ideas. *Personality and Individual Differences, 13*(3), 295–302. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(92\)90105-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(92)90105-X).
- Said-Metwaly, S., Fernández-Castilla, B., Kyndt, E., & Van den Noortgate, W. (2020). Testing conditions and creative performance: Meta-analyses of the impact of time limits and instructions. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts, 14*(1), 15–38. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000244>
- Schraw, G. (2009). A conceptual analysis of five measures of metacognitive monitoring. *Metacognition and Learning, 4*(1), 33–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-008-9031-3>
- Schunk, D. H. (2008). Metacognition, self-regulation, and self-regulated learning: Research recommendations. *Educational Psychology Review, 20*(4), 463–467. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-008-9086-3>
- Shea, N., Boldt, A., Bang, D., Yeung, N., Heyes, C., & Frith, C. D. (2014). Supra-personal cognitive control and metacognition. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 18*(4), 186–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2014.01.006>
- Shekhar, M., & Rahnev, D. (2021a). The nature of metacognitive inefficiency in perceptual decision making. *Psychological Review, 128*(1), 45–70. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000249>
- Shin, H., Cotter, K. N., Christensen, A. P., & Silvia, P. J. (2020). Creative fixation is no laughing matter: The effects of funny and unfunny examples on humor production. *The Journal of Creative Behavior, 54*(2), 487–494. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.383>

- Sidi, Y., Torgovitsky, I., Soibelman, D., Miron-Spektor, E., & Ackerman, R. (2020). You may be more original than you think: Predictable biases in self-assessment of originality. *Acta Psychologica*, 203, 103002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2019.103002>
- Silvia, P. J. (2008). Discernment and creativity: How well can people identify their most creative ideas? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 2(3), 139. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1931-3896.2.3.139>.
- Silvia, P. J., Nusbaum, E. C., & Beaty, R. E. (2017). Old or new? Evaluating the old/new scoring method for divergent thinking tasks. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 51(3), 216-224. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.101>
- Silvia, P. J., Winterstein, B. P., Willse, J. T., Barona, C. M., Cram, J. T., Hess, K. I., Martinez, J. L., & Richard, C. A. (2008). Assessing creativity with divergent thinking tasks: Exploring the reliability and validity of new subjective scoring methods. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 2(2), 68–85. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1931-3896.2.2.68>
- Simonton, D. K. (2011). Creativity and discovery as blind variation: Campbell's (1960) BVSR model after the half-century mark. *Review of General Psychology*, 15, 158–174. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022912>
- Smith, K. A., Huber, D. E., & Vul, E. (2013). Multiply-constrained semantic search in the Remote Associates Test. *Cognition*, 128(1), 64–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2013.03.001>
- Smith, K. A., & Vul, E. (2013). Sources of uncertainty in intuitive physics. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, 5(1), 185-199. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12009>
- Smith, S. M., & Blankenship, S. E. (1991). Incubation and the persistence of fixation in problem solving. *American Journal of Psychology*, 104, 61-87. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1422851>
- Smith, S. M., Ward, T. B., & Schumacher, J. S. (1993). Constraining effects of examples in a creative generations task. *Memory & Cognition*, 21(6), 837–845. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03202751>

- Sowden, P. T., Pringle, A., & Gabora, L. (2015). The shifting sands of creative thinking: Connections to dual-process theory. *Thinking & Reasoning, 21*(1), 40-60. doi: 10.1080/13546783.2014.885464
- Stanovich, K. E. (2012). On the distinction between rationality and intelligence: Implications for understanding individual differences in reasoning. In K. J. Holyoak & R. G. Morrison (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of thinking and reasoning* (pp. 433–455). Oxford University Press.
- Sternberg, R. J., & Lubart, T. I. (1992). Buy low and sell high: An investment approach to creativity. *Current Directions in Psychological Science, 1*(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.ep10767737>
- Stevens Jr, C. E., & Zabelina, D. L. (2019). Creativity comes in waves: an EEG-focused exploration of the creative brain. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences, 27*, 154-162
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2019.02.003>
- Storm, B. C., & Hickman, M. L. (2015). Mental fixation and metacognitive predictions of insight in creative problem solving. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Experimental Psychology, 68*(4), 802– 813. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17470218.2014.966730>
- Swanson, H. L. (1990). Influence of metacognitive knowledge and aptitude on problem solving. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 82*(2), 306–314. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.82.2.306>
- Threadgold, E., Marsh, J. E., McLatchie, N., & Ball, L. J. (2019). Background music stints creativity: Evidence from compound remote associate tasks. *Applied Cognitive Psychology, 33*(5), 873–888. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3532>
- Torrance, E. P. (1974). *Torrance test of creative thinking*. Scholastic Testing Service.
- Urban, M., & Urban, K. (2021). Unskilled but aware of it? Cluster analysis of creative metacognition from preschool age to early adulthood. *The Journal of Creative Behavior, 55*(4), 937–945. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.499>
- Urban, M., & Urban, K. (2022). Orientation Toward Intrinsic Motivation Mediates the Relationship

Between Metacognition and Creativity. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.558>

van Broekhoven, K., Belfi, B., Borghans, L., & Seegers, P. (2022). Creative idea forecasting: The effect of task exposure on idea evaluation. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 16(3), 519–528. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aca0000426>

van de Kamp, M.-T., Admiraal, W., van Drie, J., & Rijlaarsdam, G. (2015). Enhancing divergent thinking in visual arts education: Effects of explicit instruction of meta-cognition. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 85(1), 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12061>

Veenman, M. V. J., Van Hout-Wolters, B. H. A. M., & Afflerbach, P. (2006). Metacognition and learning: Conceptual and methodological considerations. *Metacognition and Learning*, 1(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-006-6893-0>

Vieira, S., Kannengiesser, U., & Benedek, M. (2022). Investigating triple process theory in design protocols. *Proceedings of the Design Society*, 2, 61-70. doi:10.1017/pds.2022.7

Walcher, S., Körner, C., & Benedek, M. (2017). Looking for ideas: Eye behavior during goal-directed internally focused cognition. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 53, 165-175. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-020-02068-1>

Wallach, M. A., & Kogan, N. (1965). *Modes of thinking in young children: A study of the creativity–intelligence distinction*. Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.

Weisberg, R. W. (2020). *Rethinking creativity: Inside-the-box thinking as the basis for innovation*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108785259>

Wetzstein, A., & Hacker, W. (2004). Reflective verbalization improves solutions—The effects of question-based reflection in design problem solving. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 18(2), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.949>

Yang, W., Green, A. E., Chen, Q., Kenett, Y. N., Sun, J., Wei, D., & Qiu, J. (2022). Creative problem solving

in knowledge-rich contexts. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 26(10), 849-859.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2022.06.012>

Zabelina, D. L. (2018). Attention and creativity. In R. E. Jung & O. Vartanian (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of the neuroscience of creativity* (pp. 161–179). Cambridge University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316556238.010>

Zhang, W., Sjoerds, Z., & Hommel, B. (2020). Metacontrol of human creativity: The neurocognitive mechanisms of convergent and divergent thinking. *NeuroImage*, 210, 116572.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.116572>

Zielińska, A., Lebuda, I., Ivcevic, Z., & Karwowski, M. (2022). How adolescents develop and implement their ideas? On self-regulation of creative action. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 43, 100998.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.100998>

Zimmerman, B. J. (2013). From cognitive modeling to self-regulation: A social cognitive career path.

Educational Psychologist, 48(3), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2013.794676>

Zohar, A., & Ben David, A. (2009). Paving a clear path in a thick forest: A conceptual analysis of a metacognitive component. *Metacognition and Learning*, 4(3), 177–195.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-009-9044-6>